

D4.3 – Report and content on Summer Schools

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List of abbreviations

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
TUD	Delft University of Technology
LUT	Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology
UNIM	University of Miskolc

1. Executive Summary

This document discusses the approaches to develop and organize the summer schools, the content of the summer schools, an evaluation, and the lessons learnt. It also gives insight to how participants were attracted, which instructors contributed to the contents and how different channels were used to communicate about the summer schools.

The three partners each have a leading and coordinating role in developing one of the summer schools. This results in having three distinct approaches in realizing the content and programs. Organizing a summer school has several aims. Top aims are to start in-depth academic discussions around a desired topic, while bringing researchers with different backgrounds and perspectives together. The summer school program should accommodate both aims.

General objectives for the summer schools:

- Learning about research methods of enabling the participants (junior and senior researchers) to find research gaps and academic value in their own projects, proposals and studies;
- Gaining experience in project proposal and consortium development to generate new funding opportunities;
- Working in an interactive environment, in which individual research topics are presented to and discussed with other participants and the lecturers;
- Getting to know and learning from, other researchers and developing long-term collaborations.
- Developing researcher’s communication skills such as presenting one’s own research at a conference.

Specific objectives of the first summer school on Circular Manufacturing were to provide the participants with the following:

- Developing an understanding of low carbon transition technologies for design and manufacturing, (critical) materials concerns, and waste elimination;
- Gaining insight into existing circular design theories and methods to enable circular strategies to be enacted;

Specific objectives of the second Summer School on Processing technologies in materials recycling were to provide the participants with the following:

- Developing an understanding of separation technologies, (critical) materials concerns, and waste elimination by recycling and recovery processes;
- Obtaining an awareness of value creation, innovative and entrepreneurial thinking in research collaboration;
- Gaining insight into geopolitics, and mining and minerals industry in EU to enable circular strategies to be enacted in energy transition actions;

Specific objectives of the third Summer School on Multi-disciplinarity around Circular Economy were to provide the participants with the following:

- Encourage critical thinking and systems-level analysis, equipping participants with the tools to approach complex problems holistically and to integrate social, economic, and technical dimensions in their research.

- Enhance soft skills essential for research and innovation, including communication, teamwork, and stakeholder engagement, thereby preparing participants for leadership roles in both academic and applied research settings.

The summer schools were well received. Participants gained a lot of value and experience from the well-structured programs with a variety of types of learning experiences (lectures, workshops and field trips), meeting fellow researchers from adjacent research fields, and the possibility to visit other universities. Points for improvement were related to the intensity of the timing and content, which at times was a bit high, the need for more interaction and social activities was mentioned, as well as involvement of other universities outside of the EU project partners.

2. Introduction

This document is a result from task 4.4: ‘Summer school for PhD students and junior researchers’ that focused on the development of three summer schools on three different topics: Circular manufacturing - 2023 (TUD), Processing technologies in waste recycling – 2024 (LUT), and Urban and waste mining - 2025 (UNIM). The summer schools are meant to cover the latest circular economy science and innovation issues.

This task correlates to all tasks in workpackage 4, since materials used in one educational element can be used in other elements as well. Besides, it links to task 1.2 on the knowledge exchange for project management and coordination, task 2.1 on the development of the cross organizational research teams and 2.2 on identifying research gaps, task 3.4 on staff exchanges, and task 3.6, the development of future structures to support international project activity.

2.1. Document Scope

The deliverable for task 4.4 is to organize three summer schools throughout the duration of the CiRCLETECH project. This translates into organizing one summer school each year. The organization of the summer schools is divided over the three project partners. The first summer school was organized by TUD in May 2023, the second summer school was organized by LUT in June 2024, and the third and last summer school was organized by UNIM in May 2025.

This document discusses the approaches to develop and organize the summer schools, the content of the summer schools, an evaluation, and the lessons learnt. It also gives insight to how participants were attracted, which instructors contributed to the contents and how different channels were used to communicate about the summer schools.

2.2. Methodology

The three partners each have a leading and coordinating role in developing one of the summer schools. This results in having three distinct approaches in realizing the content and programs. Detailed descriptions of these approaches can be found in the following paragraphs.

2.2.1. Summer School 1: Circular Manufacturing (TUD)

The approach to develop the set-up and program for this Summer School consisted of two phases. In the first phase, a program concept was created on the back of examples of past summer school programs in the discipline of design engineering. The development was done by two TU Delft researchers in the field of circular manufacturing.

The second phase consisted of a co-creation approach. The concept program developed in phase 1 was shared with the CiRCLETECH project partners to receive feedback, suggestions, and additions. This initially took place in e-mails and was followed-up by a Teams meeting for further discussion. Based on the input from project partners, the concept program was further developed into a new version, and the contribution and roles of all partners were determined.

As a final step, the program was sent to a professor experienced in organizing events and summer schools to further finetune the set-up. Based on the feedback, a final version of the summer school set-up was developed. External instructors were involved accordingly.

2.2.2. Summer School 2: Processing technologies in materials recycling (LUT)

The initial Summer School title “Processing technologies in waste recycling” was renewed to “Processing technologies in materials recycling” which better corresponds the zero-waste ideology of Circular Economy. LUT's core CiRCLETECH project group was mostly responsible for the background work and the planning of the Summer School 2 program. These people working in research, teaching and administrative tasks are experienced in building study programs and courses in the field of engineering and business sciences. The wishes and expectations received from the partners and the feedback from the previous summer school were considered in the program concept design.

The contents of the summer school wanted to be more consistent with the current research topics and questions around the sufficiency of raw materials in the EU regions. Therefore, the Xplorer conference 2024 - Mining and Minerals Amid Geopolitics and Energy Transition organized at LUT University at the same time was included in the Summer School program.

In this way, an extensive training program was built, that aims to support the participants' thematic knowledge, boost networking, and promote research skills, such as presenting one's own research to an audience of experts. LUT and LAB researchers were involved for lectures on thematic topics accordingly. TU Delft contributed to the facilitation of workshops included in the Summer School.

2.2.3. Summer School 3: Multi-disciplinarity around Circular Economy (UNIM)

The title of the summer school was changed in response to add the energy dimension of the CiRCLETECH Project. The new title is “Multi-disciplinarity around Circular Economy,” (before: ‘Urban and waste mining’) which reflects the multidisciplinary nature of the project spanning the four research groups. The change of the school theme was in consultation with the partners and by taking their feedback and lessons learned during the previous summer schools at TUD and LUT.

As the new summer school title, the programme included a First-day technical lectures covering engineering-themed topics with experts and lecturers from UNIM, TUD, and industrial partners. The second day shifted to cover the socio-economic and geopolitical side of energy, in addition to a field visit to one of UNIM's industrial partners to learn more about waste recycling and energy production. The third day focused more on building researchers' soft skills, including two sessions on systems thinking offered by a colleague from TUD and followed by research and partnership development, and science café.

The summer school offered the opportunity for the participants to take part in the organized multidisciplinary conference (microCAD), which was organized in conjunction with the summer school, covering topics related to various disciplines. In this way, we aimed to develop the researchers' research competencies, boost their understanding of current research needs, and facilitate collaboration opportunities.

2.3. Document Structure

The main content of this report is divided over three chapters, 3, 4, and 5, each representing a summer school. These chapters all follow the same structure. The first section discusses the content development of the summer school program, which includes the aims, times, and dates. The second section reports on the way the summer schools are organized and the

instructors which were involved. It presents an overview of the required roles and tasks of contributors/ organizers, and it introduces the instructors. The third section discusses the recruitment of participants, requirements for participation, and channels of communication. The fourth section presents dissemination activities and an evaluation of the summer school. The final section summarizes the conclusions. The chapters presenting the main content is followed up by a chapter which draws main conclusions of the results as well as reflections on the level of success.

Figure 1 Introduction of the participants.

3. Summer School 1: Circular Manufacturing (TUD)

This section presents the content and content development process of the summer school. It will discuss the aim of the course, the mix of activity types and the full summer school program and time schedule.

3.1. Program development

Organizing a summer school has several aims. Top aims are to start in-depth academic discussions around a desired topic, while bringing researchers with different backgrounds and perspectives together. The summer school program should accommodate both aims. Therefore, the schedule was structured to have a mix of activity types which foster in-depth learning (content), as well as allowing the researchers learn and discover the context (culture) in which the summer school is held and get to know each other in a formal and more informal way (social).

3.1.1. Date, times, and location

The summer school took place from 22 May 2023 16:00 CEST to 25 May 2023 18:00 CEST at Delft University of Technology, Delft, the Netherlands.

3.1.2. Aim of the course

The main aim of the course was to support PhDs and Postdocs, who are working on topics related to Circular Manufacturing to become better informed and equipped for their research, by (i) helping to develop a research direction, and (ii) encouraging discussion and collaboration.

The objectives of the summer school were to provide the participants with the following:

- Developing an understanding of low carbon transition technologies for design and manufacturing, (critical) materials concerns, and waste elimination;
- Gaining insight into existing circular design theories and methods to enable circular strategies to be enacted;
- Learning about research methods to enable the PhD students to find research gaps and academic value in their own projects, proposals and studies;
- Gaining experience in project proposal and consortium development to generate new funding opportunities;
- Working in an interactive environment, in which individual research topics are presented to and discussed with other participants and the lecturers;
- Getting to know and learning from, other researchers and developing long-term collaborations.

To achieve these objectives, the participants are actively engaged in the Summer School: the emphasis is on discussions and exercises based around the research projects of the participants.

3.1.3. Content development

To facilitate in-depth learning, a mix of activity types was selected in which the content was offered.

- 3 Personal grant development sessions

Applying for personal grants is one of the keys to building a career in academia. Oftentimes young researchers are not trained in the process of proposal writing and might not be aware of the opportunities to apply for personal grants.

- 2 Circular design method workshops

Circular design methods contain loads of (academic) knowledge on the topic of circular manufacturing and are a highly accessible way of learning (learning-by-doing).

- 1xlab workshops

Practical work makes theories come to life. Exploring and experimenting foster fast and enjoyable learning.

- 8 Lectures

To lay the basis for the theoretical thinking frame of the project, a series of lectures was organized. Half of these lectures were focused on explaining the theoretical concepts behind circular manufacturing. The other half were guest presentations from industry about how to apply circularity or how to conduct research.

These activities together formed the following program:

Summer School Program

Time Schedule (in Central European Summer Time)

Monday 22.05.2023

Time	Location	Activity
16:30- 17:30	't Postkantoor Hippolytusbuurt 14, Delft city center	Get-together, welcome.
17:30-20:00	't Postkantoor	Dinner
20:00		Get settled in hotels

Tuesday 23.05.2023

Time	Location	Activity	Lecturer
09:15- 09:45		Walk-in, coffee	
09:45- 10:15	Berlagezaal 2 Faculty of Architecture Julianalaan 134, Delft campus	(1) Introducing Delft, TU Delft, focus Circular Delft Impact – 45 mins	Jan-Henk Welink
10:15- 10:30		Break	

10:30- 12:00	Berlagezaal 2	(1) Structure and objectives for the Summer School – 30 mins What are your expectations? <i>Break out in groups of 3-4</i> (2) Personal grant development 1/4 – How to write a successful grant – 60 mins	Nina Boorsma Nela Kapelan
12:00- 13:30		Lunch and campus sight-seeing	
13:30- 15:00	Berlagezaal 2	(1) Lecture 1/8: Circular Manufacturing - 45 mins <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Introduction to remanufacturing principles & practice• The remanufacturing process• Circular business models, circular supply chains, and partnerships (2) Circular Design Method 1/2: Remanufacturing Checklist – 45 mins <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Introduction to method• Select case/ product• Putting the method to practice• Present and discuss results	Jan-Henk Welink Nina Boorsma Jan-Henk Welink
15:00- 15:15		Break	
15:15- 16:30	Berlagezaal 2	(2) Circular Design Method 2/2: Circular Product Readiness method – 75 mins <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Introduction to method• Case/ product introduction• Putting the method to practice• Present and discuss results	Nina Boorsma
16:30- 17:30		Walk to restaurant	
17:30- 20:00	De Waag Markt 11, Delft city center	Dinner	

Wednesday 24.05.2023

Time	Location	Topic	Lecturer
09:00- 09:30		Walk-in, coffee	
09:30- 10:15	BG.Oost.490 Faculty of Architecture Julianalaan 134, Delft campus	(1) Lecture (online) 2/8: Scientific writing	Prof. Norbert Sabó
10:15- 10:30		Break	

10:30- 12:00	BG.Oost.490	(1) Lecture 3/8: Open science practices (2) Personal grant development 2/4 – Preparation of a grant: Personal vs Collaborative – 60 mins	Beáta Kovács Szabóné Jan Schiereck Frank Versluis
12:00- 13:15		Lunch and campus sight-seeing	
13:15- 15:00	BG.Oost.490	(1) Lecture 4/8: Model for asset manufacturers – 45 mins • Eco-cost vs. Lifecycle Cost (2) Lecture 5/8: Driving and encouraging sustainability through Emerson factory automation. – 45 mins • From new product development to product recycling	Jenny Coenen Diana Precup (Emerson Automation Solutions FCP Kft.)
15:00- 15:15		Break	
15:15- 16:30	BG.Oost.490	(1) Lecture 6/8: Industrial and policy trends – 30 mins (2) Lecture 7/8: Resources for circular manufacturing- 30 mins • Critical materials - Strategic importance, Mitigation strategies • Materials recycling	Jan-Henk Welink Jan-Henk Welink
16:30- 17:30		Free time	
17:30- 20:00	Café de Wijnhaven Wijnhaven 22, Delft city center	Dinner	

Thursday 25.05.2023

Time	Location	Topic	Lecturer
08:30- 09:00		Walk-in, coffee	
09:00- 10:00	Central hall The Hague University/ Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences Delft: Rotterdamseweg 137, Delft campus	(1) Workshop 1/2: Remanufacturing in practice - setting up a factory workshop – 60 mins • How to translate a Remanufacturing Process Map into a tangible, (dirty) hands-on experience in a reman workshop • Demos HR and HHS student projects • First-hand examples from an industry case of Hitachi Construction Machinery Europe • Dealing with design-for-reman products and not-designed-for-reman products • Difficulties in selling remanufactured products • Development of a roadmap to establish an operational workshop and sales	Jenny Coenen Marten Bootsma

10:15- 10:30		Break	
10:30- 12:00	Central hall	(1) Workshop 2/2: Remanufacturing in practice - setting up a factory workshop – 90 mins	Jenny Coenen Marten Bootsma
12:00- 13:30		Lunch and campus sight-seeing	
13:30- 15:00	Zaal B Faculty of Architecture Julianalaan 134, Delft campus	(1) Lecture (online) 8/8: Sustainable solutions in Power Tool development	Dr. József Kakuk (Bosch)
15:00- 15:15		Break	
15:15- 17:00	Zaal B	(1) Personal grant development 3/4 – Grant writing: tips, assignments, discussions – 60 mins (2) Personal grant development 4/4 – Drafting the final concept note (one-pager) – 30 mins	Nela Kapelan Frank Versluis Nela Kapelan Frank Versluis
17:00- 18:00	Zaal B	Concluding the Summer School	

3.1.4. Shared folder

A shared folder was created to give the participants access to general information, background information and literature, lecture slides and introductory slides of all participants.

Figure 2 Folder structure of the shared folder for the summer school participants.

Figure 3 Kick-off of the summer school - introducing the program.

3.2. Organization and instructors

This section discusses the roles and associated tasks for organizing a summer school. It also lists all the instructors who were involved in the process.

3.2.1. Organization

To bring the summer school to a success, there are several roles to fulfil. These roles can be divided among several organizers. The lists below discuss all the roles and associated tasks that need to be fulfilled to organize a summer school.

Organizer (2)

- Determine the times and dates – together with project partners
- Propose options for the accommodations to those who need to travel from far
- Prepare program contents and activities
- Reach out to instructors for contributions
- Send invitations and a description of the summer school to potential participants
- Set up a shared folder with course contents
- Analyse the evaluation forms
- Monitor the budget
- Organize gifts for the instructors/ contributors
- Manage GDPR requirements
- Request dietary preferences from participants
- Optional: invite a special guest to open the summer school, perhaps a dean, ambassador, industry partner or member of the European Commission
- Optional: prepare a goodie bag with a nice book and/ or local souvenir for the participants

Moderator (2)

- Welcome the group
- Introduce the program, speakers/ instructors, and program elements
- Provide information about the schedule
- Lead the group between locations
- Lead tours (through the city, over the campus)
- Closing words of the summer school

Assistant (1)

- Book rooms
- Organize lunch and coffee
- Set up guest wifi
- Arrange post-its and flip-overs
- Arrange pointers and cables etc.,
- Trouble shooting.

Instructors (5-10)

- Prepare and deliver lectures
- Organize and lead tours
- Organize and deliver workshops
- Prepare and lead assignments

Disseminator (1)

- Create promotional materials
- Promote the summer school on social media
- Take photos
- Record videos
- Draft social media messages
- Distribute and collect the evaluation forms

Figure 4 Summer school participants during a lecture.

3.2.2. Instructors

We had the honor of working with a knowledgeable and diverse group of instructors. Four of these instructors were selected by our colleagues at the university of Miskolc. The instructors gave guest lectures about research skills or they represented an industrial party. Two instructors work at The Hague University of Applied Sciences. They gave lectures and organized a practical lab workshop. The remaining six instructors work at the TU Delft. A short description of the roles and background of each of the instructors is provided below.

[Dr. József Kakuk](#)

Graduated as a certified mechanical engineer in 2003 at the University of Miskolc, in 2005 he obtained a PhD degree as well. Over the past 20 years, he has gained extensive experience in engineering and development at large industrial companies. He spent nearly 18 years at Robert Bosch Power Tool Kft., where he was responsible for various areas of Engineering as a manager. As Engineering Director, he was responsible for the full management of the development engineering of DIY and garden tools. Additionally, he is currently teaching at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Informatics of the University of Miskolc as honorary associate professor. From January 2025, he joined the Engineering Division of the Bay Zoltán Research Institute, where as Division Director, his task is to manage and support the Miskolc team with excellent expertise and to make maximum use of the unique research infrastructure.

Prof. Norbert Sabó

Prof. Dr. Norbert Péter Szabó is a geophysicist and full professor at the University of Miskolc, where he also serves as Head of the Department of Geophysics and Vice-Dean for Scientific Affairs. He earned his MSc in Geophysical Engineering in 1999 and PhD in 2005, and defended his DSc at the Hungarian Academy of Sciences in 2020. His research focuses on geophysical inversion, multivariate statistical methods, and their applications in water and hydrocarbon exploration. He is also a senior research fellow at the MTA-ME Geoengineering Research Group and has participated in numerous national and EU-funded R&D projects.

[Diana Precup](#)

Diana Precup is an industrial engineer and quality systems specialist with extensive experience in project leadership and engineering operations at Emerson Automation FCP Kft. She currently serves as a Non-NPD Project Leader, where she leads cross-functional teams and drives continuous improvement initiatives. Diana is also deeply engaged in mentoring and community-building activities, including serving as a team leader for Women Impact and as a mentor and jury member for the International Pneumobile Contest.

She holds a master's degree in quality system management and an Industrial Engineering degree from the University "Petru Maior" in Romania, with additional academic experience through Erasmus programs in Germany and Spain. Diana has participated in several international technical competitions and conferences and has explored innovative topics such as energy generation using intelligent materials. Her work is driven by a commitment to technical excellence, collaboration, and empowering the next generation of engineers.

[Beáta Kovács Szabóné.](#)

Acting general director, senior librarian at the University of Miskolc Library, Archives, and Museum. In her work, in addition to traditional library services, she also focuses on electronic information services and access to information. She is focusing on the activities of libraries in support of research and publishing, and the integration of new opportunities, especially open science/access, into the workflow of a University library.

[Prof. Jenny Coenen](#)

Professor Smart Sustainable Manufacturing at The Hague University of Applied Sciences

Professor Jenny Coenen obtained her PhD in the field of Ship Production. She has worked as researcher, lecturer, developer and consultant at Royal IHC, Delft University of Technology, Bloem Doze Nienhuis (a maritime consultancy company in Rotterdam), and Shipping & Transport College (STC) Rotterdam. Her key interests and expertise are the improvement of (collaboration in) the production chain, engineering and business processes; both within companies as between companies.

[Marten Bootsma](#)

Coordinator Circular Makers Industry and Lecturer in the Automotive course, at Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences.

Core to his work is to promote the relevance of technical education in circularity challenges. He likes to create the win-win of applied circularity in businesses and contribute to improved student knowledge and skills. Marten has 20+ years of experience in international after sales in the automotive and construction machinery industry, working for (Japanese) manufacturers,

Hitachi Construction Machinery (Europe), of which 10+ years as manager. He fulfilled various roles, in one of them he was responsible for the start-up and development of the remanufacturing department, contributing an annual turnover of EUR 3M @ 20% GPM (Gross Profit Margin) to the company's results.

[Dr. David Peck](#)

Associate professor circular manufacturing and materials, Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment, Delft University of Technology. The activities includes 21st century sustainability challenges, resource constraints, critical raw materials, circular cities - business, innovation, scarcity history, companies and critical materials, governmental (EU member state and EU) policy towards resources and new closed loop business models. David teaches on the opportunities and challenges regarding circular innovation and circular business models. Research has a focus on the opportunities arising from critical (scarce) materials and circular business solutions in the international urban context. David is the university lead for the Ellen MacArthur Pioneer University membership. David is a manager of large EU projects. He was the principal investigator in EU 1 FP7 (CRM Innonet) and 2 H2020 projects (ERN - remanufacturing & ProSUM - Urban Mine). Current H2020 is called Pop-Machina.

[Dr. Nina Boorsma](#)

Postdoctoral researcher circular manufacturing and industrial entrepreneurship, Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment, Delft University of Technology.

Nina's main role is with the Innovation Team at the Port of Rotterdam Authority where it is her team's mission to accelerate innovation within the organization, where possible together with eco-system partners in the port, towards realizing increased efficiency, sustainability, circularity, and great port-user experiences.

She combines this with a Postdoc, in which she focused on the implementation of remanufacturing in various industries, more specifically, on entrepreneurship and the early phase of the design process. One of her aims is to translate knowledge into tools and methods that are useful in practice. In the future, Nina would like to set up more experiments with companies to explore the possibilities for remanufacturing. In the past, she has completed a PhD on Strategic Design for Remanufacturing.

[Nela Kapelan](#)

EIT KICs coordinator and grant advisor, EU funding team, Innovation&Impact Centre, Delft University of Technology

She has a background in Research Management at the University of Exeter in the UK where she worked for almost 20 year as the research services humanities cluster lead.

In her current role she works together with different faculties. The university is involved in 5 KICs she's managing the relationships and, in the case of the CiRCLETECH project, she's more involved in the content of the project as well.

[Jan-Henk Welink](#)

Project Lead, secretary and initiator, the faculty of Mechanical Engineering

Jan-Henk works on setting up and leading projects on sustainable resource management, especially in the field of critical materials, waste management, and industrial symbiosis.

He runs a knowledge platform on responsible and sustainable resource management, based at the TU Delft. Where he makes the existing scientific knowledge on this topic available to companies. This platform has a network function in the academic world on this topic. In his capacity he organizes seminars, master classes and expert meetings.

[Jan Schiereck](#)

EU Research grant advisor, EU funding team, Innovation&Impact Centre, Delft University of Technology

Experienced Research Advisor with a demonstrated history of working in the research industry. Skilled in Sustainable Development, Sustainability, Renewable Energy, Energy Policy, and Energy. Strong community and social services professional with an MBE, master of business in energy systems, from Technische Universiteit Delft.

[Frank Versluis](#)

EU Research grant advisor, EU funding team, Innovation&Impact Centre, Delft University of Technology

Frank has a background as a researcher at Leiden Institute of Chemistry, Leiden University, where he studied peptides, gels, supramolecular chemistry and more.

3.3. Participation

This section addresses participant selection and network building. It explains about the requirements for the participants to be selected, the invitations that were shared with them and the means of communication with the participants.

3.3.1. Recruitment of participants

Participants - The Summer School was organized for a group of 10-12 researchers (PhDs, Postdocs) and was suitable for those who had decided on a research topic, had undertaken a literature study, had formulated the first aims and objectives and had an initial plan of work.

Research profile – We asked the participants to complete a research profile and send a pdf to their university contact person to apply for the Summer School (Figure 5). Each partner would make a selection of the participant based on their research profile and fit.

Fee - There was no fee for this Summer School, as it was funded by Horizon Europe EU project CIRCLETECH.

RESEARCH PROFILE

[INSERT A HEAD SHOT OR
A RESEARCH FIGURE/ VISUAL]

ABOUT [FIRST NAME]
[Where I'm from, highlight of the year, me in 3 words, favorite quote, I always wanted to become a researcher, because.../ I never expected to become a researcher, because.]

RESEARCH PROFILE
[Research topic, research questions, methods, interests, the potential title for my upcoming journal article.]

INTEREST IN THE CIRCLETECH SUMMER SCHOOL CIRCULAR MANUFACTURING
[Type here...]

WHAT I WOULD LIKE TO LEARN
[Type here...]

[FIRST NAME] [LAST NAME]
[Affiliation]
[Research topic]

Figure 5 Template of the research profile.

3.3.2. Channels and points of contact

The first contact with the potential participants took place via the university contact person. The university contact person would bring the summer school to the attention of researchers. After selection, the university contact person shared all relevant summer school information with the participant to support them in making the needed travel arrangements.

Once arrived at the location of the summer school, the organizers, moderators and assistants guided the participants through the program elements, announcing the locations and times. A WhatsApp group was created to share any additional announcements.

After the summer school, the participants received all workshop and lecture materials through the shared folder.

Figure 6 Remanufacturing in practice workshop by The Hague University of Applied Sciences Part 1.

Figure 7 Remanufacturing in practice workshop by The Hague University of Applied Sciences part 2.

3.4. Dissemination and evaluation

This section addresses the ways in which the summer school activities were disseminated to our professional networks. It also includes an evaluation of the summer school set-up and content.

3.4.1. Dissemination

Prior to the summer school, information about the summer school was shared in relevant research groups (related to circular economy) at the three participating universities, to attract participants.

During and after the summer school, LinkedIn posts were created to inform our network about the summer school activities and content (Figure 8).

Figure 8 LinkedIn posts created during and after the summer school.

3.4.2. Evaluation

To evaluate the summer school, the participants were asked to fill in an evaluation form at the end of the summer school. The questions included in the evaluation can be found in Appendix 7.1.1. A summary of the reactions is given below.

Reactions to the timing and duration of the summer school:

- Next time it should be in the beginning of April, or a better at the middle of June. The workload and number of lectures was acceptable, but was a bit tiring.
- The organization of the program was perfect.
- Although the number of lectures was high for one day, but it was necessary for understanding everything, and being really useful, so I strongly agreed the above asked questions.
- The duration was a little bit short for this amount of materials. The summer school was at the end of the semester, when I have deadlines, it was difficult to reconcile with them, it could have been in April or June.

My state of knowledge is substantially higher than before the Summer School.

8 responses

Figure 9 Evaluation question 'State of knowledge' 1 = strongly agree, 5 = strongly disagree

The lectures were rich in variety.

8 responses

Figure 10 Evaluation question 'Lectures rich in variety' 1 = strongly agree, 5 = strongly disagree

Which activities did you enjoy most?

8 responses

Figure 11 Evaluation question 'Highest rated activity' based on number of votes

Reactions to the teaching materials and lectures:

- Most of the lectures were well prepared and interesting.
- Could be nice to have more time for LCC and reman costs calculation exercise on the last day. Also, it could be a good idea to have workshop on designing/redesigning of products to make them more circular
- The atmosphere was absolutely pleasant, I enjoyed being there with the organizer colleagues. As for me, I was not so familiar with the Circular Manufacturing, but therefore I could gain a lot of new information and techniques. Otherwise, I was interested in EU projects, high quality scientific writing, and I was happy that I could hear informations about these topics.
- I enjoyed the ones that were more direct to us and presented the theory and practice at the same time.
- Hard to choose the most enjoyable, I liked almost every lecture. The ones, which are not chosen, were not bad, just the others were better.

Reactions to a general assessment of the summer school:

- I am very happy that I could participate in a training course at one of the best universities and gain experience not only in the summer university but also in getting to know local things and principles.
- I cannot choose one thing, because I liked every aspect of the Summer School.
- I enjoyed the practical work the most, there could be more classes like this, because it is easier to learn the theory when put into practice.
- A session that let participant to present their research topics, work via posters or a short presentation. Speed meeting session can also allow to start potential collaboration for the future. We were a small group but since the agenda was full even during the dinner there was not enough time to talk with everyone about potential future collaboration or the different topics we are working on.
- Involve each partner from the project into the program.
- An organised city-seeing would be great.
- This is one of the best organized and sufficiently informative summer schools I have ever been to. There were no unnecessary lectures, the number of theory and practice was adequate. I was constantly learning and getting to know things. Sometimes we ran out of time, but even that wasn't a problem, due to the sufficient number of breaks and flexibility. I can't say anything that would raise the level noticeably.
- There was too much teaching material in too short a time, we only went through most things quickly, I think it would be better to take a smaller material, but more thoroughly.

Overall, the summer school received a positive evaluation from the participants. Valuable insights which could improve the quality of the summer school were the following: in terms of timing (preferably April or mid-June), the workload (slightly too high), the possibility to dive deep (a bit more time per element would have been good), a personal introduction of the participants would have been valuable, and a city tour would have been great.

What wasn't included in the evaluation were the food, drinks and the accommodation. Perhaps it would have been good to include an evaluation of these aspects too.

Adding a test-question to check if respondents read the answers correctly is advised. For example: 'did you join this summer school' 1= strongly agree, 5 = strongly disagree.

Additional feedback reports by three participants from the University of Miskolc can be found in Appendix 7.1.2 - 7.1.4.

Figure 12 Jan-Henk Welink introducing the group to Circular Manufacturing

3.5. Conclusions

A range of different activities are brought together in developing a summer school. There is the preparation phase, in which a program is developed, and participants are being recruited. Instructors need to be approached, and rooms need to be booked. This also includes arranging food, drinks, and proposing accommodation options for the participants. Then there is the summer school itself, where we welcome the participants and take them through the program. And finally, there is the dissemination, evaluation and reflection on the summer school.

Several generic conclusions can be drawn which are useful in organizing a summer school in the future. The first is to make sure to have enough people to organize the summer school. Divide the roles evenly over those involved to ensure the envisioned quality. In addition, get commitment from the instructors in time and align the contents. Have a variety of presenters and types of activities, and include tours and practical lab work, because this will increase participant engagement. With regards to the schedule, make sure to have enough 'air' in the schedule, allow people to connect to each other and to the city. Make sure the participants get time to digest what they've been exposed to during the day. The final point, which is relevant to upcoming summer schools, is to align the summer school program and content with the CIRCLETECH research group activities.

Generally seen, the summer school went as planned and the feedback from the participants has been very positive.

4. Summer School 2: Processing technologies in materials recycling (LUT)

This section presents the content and development process of the Summer School 2. It will discuss the aim of the course, the different activity types and the full summer school program and time schedule.

4.1. Program development

The structure and content of the summer school was designed on the basis that it offers interesting activities and topics to all researchers at different stages of their careers, not just younger researchers. In this way, researchers get to know each other and exchange ideas with a different experience base that supports learning at all levels.

LUT wanted to offer the participants of the summer school information and opportunities from a broader perspective around a current topic. The Xplorer conference organized at the same time was very suitable for this. This arrangement also made sense for practical reasons, as LUT has excellent facilities and support services for organizing even large events. This includes food and social activities as well.

Thus, the total time of the summer school was five days, two of which were at the conference. Although an organized evening activities is generally recommended, we wanted to leave some free space in the participants' social program, and the opportunity for independent activities in the evenings, e.g. in smaller groups. Thus, the planned evening program was only for one evening in the form of a lake cruise and dinner.

4.1.1. Date, times, and location

The summer school took place from Monday to Friday, June 10 – 14, 2024 at LUT University, Lappeenranta Campus, Yliopistonkatu 34, 53850 Lappeenranta Finland.

4.1.2. Aim of the course

This program has been designed for researchers focusing on circular economy and materials processing, specifically related to Critical Raw Materials. The focus will be engineering while the format will equip students with tools and experiences to help them: 1. develop their research skills, and 2. guide them through in-depth discussions and provide opportunities for collaboration and networking.

The objectives of the second Summer School were mostly similar with the first one:

- Developing an understanding of separation technologies, (critical) materials concerns, and waste elimination by recycling and recovery processes;
- Obtaining an awareness of value creation, innovative and entrepreneurial thinking in research collaboration;
- Gaining insight into geopolitics, and mining and minerals industry in EU to enable circular strategies to be enacted in energy transition actions;
- Learning about research methods of enabling the participants (junior and senior researchers) to find research gaps and academic value in their own projects, proposals and studies;

- Gaining experience in project proposal and consortium development to generate new funding opportunities, especially Horizon Europe calls;
- Working in an interactive environment, in which individual research topics are presented to and discussed with other participants and the lecturers;
- Getting to know and learning from other researchers and developing networks for long-term collaborations.
- Developing researcher’s communication skills such as presenting one’s own research at a conference.

To achieve these objectives, the participants are actively engaged in the Summer School: the emphasis is on discussions and exercises based around the research projects of the participants.

4.1.3. Content development

To facilitate in-depth learning, different activity was selected in which the content was offered.

- 8 Lectures for the theoretical thinking frame of the project, a series of lectures was organized.
- Participating the two days conference and presenting own research by pitching and poster.
- 2 x lab visits, seeing research facilities and meet researchers at their work foster fast and enjoyable learning.
- 2 x HEU project proposal workshop sessions, group working.

These activities together formed the following program:

Summer School 2 Program

Time Schedule in Eastern European (EET) Summer Time

Monday June 10, 2024

Time	Location	Activity / Topic	Contact / Lecturer
9:00	Main lobby H1247	Meet in the main lobby. Walk-in, coffee	Miia John
9:30	H1247	(1) Welcome to LUT (2) Summer School 2 Intro, Programme and Objectives (3) Separation technologies and CE, SCI-MAT Platform	Matti Lampinen Miia John Sami Virolainen
~10:30		Break	
10:45	H1247	(1) Hydrometallurgy (2) Solid-liquid separation	Manivannan Sethurajan Teemu Kinnarinen

12:15	Restaurant Skinnarila	Lunch	
13:00	H1247	(1) Materials recovery and Additive manufacturing (2) Battery recycling	Eveliina Repo Ekaterina Laakso
~14:30	H1247	Break, coffee	
14:45		Separation science department Laboratory visit	Liisa Puro
15:45 – 16:00	H1247	Feedback discussion	

Tuesday – Wednesday June 11–12, 2024

Xplorer Conference 2024 - Mining and Minerals amid Geopolitics and Energy Transition

- <https://www.lut.fi/en/xplorer/xplorer-conference#toc--program-at-a-glance->
- June 11, 19:00–22:00, Social program – A dinner cruise on Lake Saimaa
- CIRCLETECH researchers' posters – opportunity to pitch posters and research highlights.

Thursday June 13, 2024

Time	Location	Activity	Contact / Lecturer
9:00	H2209	Walk-in, coffee	
9:30	H2209 / JHC	Innovations, JHC visit https://www.lut.fi/en/protolab-j-hyneman-center	Terhi Virkki-Hatakka Markku Ikävalko
~10:45		Break	
11:00	H2209	AI in circular value creation	Malahat Ghoreishi
12:00	Restaurant Skinnarila	Lunch and campus sightseeing	
13:00	H2209	Academic Entrepreneurship and Industry – University collaboration	Katja Lahikainen
~14:15	H2209	Break, coffee	
14:30 – 16:00	H2209	Workshop: Research ideas around CRM's – Xplorer conference, what we learned? Feedback discussion	Matti Lampinen David Peck

Friday June 14, 2024

Optional day: small groups meetings, brainstorming joint research and project proposals.

Meet your colleagues!

Time	Location	Activity
9:00	H2209	Walk-in, coffee
9:30		Small groups meetings
~(11:00) 12:00	Restaurant Skinnarila	Lunch
13:00		Small groups meetings
~13:30	Restaurant Skinnarila	Break, coffee (the restaurant closes at 14:00)
15:00	H2209	Wrap up and closing the summer school

Figure 13 Researchers gather after Friday's workshop of Summer School 2.

4.1.4. Shared folder

The course materials (files) were collected in their own folders under the same folder that was created earlier for summer school 1. (Figure 14) In addition, the conference material was collected in a separate folder. That includes e.g. books of abstracts.

Figure 14 Shared folder in Teams, the Summer School 2 materials.

4.2. Organization and staff

This section discusses the roles and associated tasks for organizing a summer school. It also lists in detail the instructors who were involved in the process.

4.2.1. Organization

The roles and tasks in summer school organization team were somewhat merged with the ones in conference organization team, because these events were developed and arranged simultaneously. Thus, only a couple of people were responsible for all tasks related to summer school. Many sub-tasks are part of the daily work and tasks of university's facility and support service staff and thus cannot reasonably include here.

Organizer / Moderator (2 CiRCLETECH + 2 Xplorer)

- Determine the times and dates – together with project partners
- Propose options for the accommodations to those who need to travel from far
- Prepare program contents and activities
- Reach out to instructors for contributions
- Send invitations and a description of the summer school to potential participants
- Set up a shared folder with course contents
- Prepare, send and analyse the evaluation forms
- Monitor the budget
- Manage GDPR requirements
- Request dietary preferences from participants

- Welcome the group
- Introduce the program, speakers/ instructors, and program elements
- Provide information about the schedule
- Lead the group between locations over the campus

- Closing words of the summer school
- Book rooms
- Organize lunch and coffee
- Set up guest wifi
- Arrange post-its and flip-overs
- Arrange pointers and cables etc.,
- Trouble shooting
- Dissemination

Instructors (9)

- Prepare and deliver lectures
- Organize and lead tours
- Organize and deliver workshops
- Prepare and lead assignments

4.2.2. Instructors

Instructors gave lectures on thematic topics from their own specialty research field and/or led laboratory tours. Most of them work at LUT University, one at LAB university and one visitor lecturer Dr. David Peck at TU Delft. In addition, Xplorer conference brought together experts from different countries, companies, and academia. Altogether 21 specialists gave lectures on various topics around mining and minerals industry and landscape. A short description of the instructors (lecturers) is provided in the next section.

[Malahat Ghoreishi](#)

PhD, Senior lecturer and researcher, LAB University of Applied Sciences

Economics and Business Administration, Artificial Intelligence in circular value creation

[Teemu Kinnarinen](#)

D.Sc. (Tech.), Associate professor, LUT University

Chemical engineering, Solid-liquid separation

[Ekaterina Laakso](#)

PhD, Associate professor, LUT University

Chemical engineering, Materials for the electrochemical energy storage and material recycling

[Katja Lahikainen](#)

D.Sc., Director LUT Centre for Separation Technology (CST), LUT University

Economics and Business Administration, University-based ecosystems; academic entrepreneurship; university-industry collaboration; entrepreneurship education

[Liisa Puro](#)

D.Sc. (Tech.), Analysis engineer, LUT University

Chemical engineering, Analysis of inorganic and organic compounds, material characterization

[Eveliina Repo](#)

D.Sc. (Tech.), Professor, LUT University

Chemical engineering, Hydrometallurgy for urban mining

[Manivannan Sethurajan](#)

PhD, Post-doctoral researcher, LUT University

Chemical engineering, Biological and chemical hydrometallurgy

[Terhi Virkki-Hatakka](#)

D.Sc. (Tech.), Project manager at School of Business and Management, LUT University
Doctoral education, Sustainable business, Prototyping, innovations and entrepreneurship

[Sami Virolainen](#)

D.Sc. (Tech.), Docent, Associate professor, Head of Department of Separation Science, LUT University

Chemical engineering, Industrial hydrometallurgy

Figure 15 On the first lecture of Summer School 2.

4.3. Participation

This section addresses the recruitment process and network building. It explains about the criteria for participation, the invitations (*i.e.* information letter) that were shared and other means of communication.

4.3.1. Recruitment of participants

An invitation letter was drawn up by LUT to recruit participants. The letter contained information about the schedule and content of the course. Each partner was independently responsible for distributing the invitation to their own researchers. After this, the partners compiled the course registrations (including dietary details etc.) and delivered them to the course organizer.

The basis for participating in the course was the researcher's own interest in the topic and collaboration opportunities in the project, and the need for personal development as a researcher. Hence, any internal or external evaluation criteria for participation based on e.g. “research profile and fit” was not used. Nevertheless, the enrolment to the Summer School included the registration to Xplorer conference as well. Preparing a poster, and the submission of an abstract was highly recommended even though not mandatory.

There was no fee for this Summer School or conference, as it was funded by Horizon Europe EU project CiRCLETECH. Travelling costs were covered by the project as well.

4.3.2. Channels and points of contact

Similarly, as in previous summer school, the first contact with the potential participants took place via the university contact person. The university contact person would bring the summer school to the attention of researchers. After selection, the university contact person shared all relevant summer school information with the participants to support them in making the needed travel arrangements.

Once arrived at the location of the summer school, the organizers guided the participants through the program elements, announcing the locations and times. When the location was different to previous days, the people met in the main entrance lobby first in the morning.

After the summer school, the participants received all workshop and lecture materials through the shared folder.

Figure 16 Summer School participants starting the lake cruise dinner.

4.4. Dissemination and evaluation

4.4.1. Communication and dissemination

Prior to the summer school, information about the course was shared in relevant research groups (related to circular economy) at the three participating universities, to attract participants. The Summer School brought together 14 researchers and 11 instructors/lecturers, of which some also participated the workshops as researchers.

The CiRCLETECH project was introduced in Xplorer conference together with posters and pitching presentations by summer school participants. Two CiRCLETECH researchers, David Peck and America Quinteros Condorety acted as speakers in the conference as well. Book of abstracts was published, open access:

https://www.lut.fi/sites/default/files/media/documents/Xplorer-posteri_abstraktit.pdf

Totally nine poster presentations were given from CiRCLETECH Summer School group. Seven of those produced by UNIM researchers.

After the Summer School, LinkedIn posts related to the CiRCLETECH were created by the conference organizer and participants as well. (Figure 17)

Figure 17 LinkedIn posts created during and after the summer school.

At the same, these organized events and mobility of researchers also offered a great opportunity to settle other meetings between researcher colleagues from different universities with similar research interests. UNIM’s researchers utilized this opportunity, e.g. by visiting the mechatronics and robotics laboratories at LUT Lappeenranta, and LUT Kouvola to meet LUT researchers in person. (Figure 18)

Figure 18 LinkedIn post about UNIM-LUT collaboration.

4.4.2. Evaluation

To evaluate the Summer School 2, the participants were asked to fill in a short and simple Webropol survey after the event. The questions included in the feedback survey can be found in Appendix 7.2.1. An individual link to survey was sent by email to 18 attendees. Totally seven responses were recorded, that makes the response rate rather low 38% though the motivation of participants was high (4.9/5). A summary of the reflection is given below.

My role in the Summer School was:

Number of respondents: 7

Figure 19 Feedback survey Q1 reflection.

My motivation over the Summer School was:
Scale: 1 - very little, 5 - very high.

Number of respondents: 7

Option: Can't say - excluded from average

Figure 20 Feedback survey Q2 reflection.

How much did you invest in this event? (Note that tasks may be e.g. meetings with colleagues.)

Number of respondents: 7

Figure 21 Feedback survey Q3 reflection.

Attending the Summer School brought me about:
Scale: 1 - very little, 5 - very much.

Number of respondents: 7

Option: Can't say - excluded from average

Figure 22 Feedback survey Q4 reflection.

The overall timing of the Summer School was appropriate.
Scale: 1 - strongly disagree, 5 - strongly agree.

Number of respondents: 7

Option: Can't say - excluded from average

Figure 23 Feedback survey Q6 reflection.

The content of the Summer School was appropriate.
Scale: 1 - strongly disagree, 5 - strongly agree

Number of respondents: 7

Option: Can't say - excluded from average

Figure 24 Feedback survey Q7 reflection.

The workload during the Summer School was appropriate.
Scale: 1 - strongly disagree, 5 - strongly agree

Number of respondents: 7

Option: Can't say - excluded from average

Figure 25 Feedback survey Q8 reflection.

The Summer School was well organized.
Scale: 1 - strongly disagree, 5 - strongly agree

Number of respondents: 7

Option: Can't say - excluded from average

Figure 26 Feedback survey Q9 reflection.

Written reflections on the question “Additional remarks, thoughts and feelings on your expectations, achievements or disappointments concerning the Summer School”:

- The Summer School was well organised, with interesting topics to discuss. We had the opportunity to hear about the researches conducted at LUT Lappeenranta, to visit their research facility and get to know their researchers. The second part of the Summer School which addressed the theme of EU project funding was also really interesting and insightful. The Explorer conference gave us a good understanding on geopolitics and energy transition. Thank you for organizing the event and for the opportunity to participate.
- My participation in the 2024 Circletech Summer School provided a wealth of invaluable experiences that have significantly advanced my academic and professional trajectory. The program offered an integrated approach, combining rigorous theoretical lectures, practical workshops, and interactive sessions designed to deepen understanding and facilitate the application of circular manufacturing principles. A key highlight of the program was the Xplorer Conference, which brought together a diverse cohort of participants from various countries and academic disciplines. This diversity fostered a rich collaborative environment where we exchanged insights, addressed challenges, and discussed solutions pertinent to our respective fields. At the conference, I had the opportunity to present my research poster. The focal point of my research was the comprehensive analysis of the lifecycle costs and environmental impacts of a newly developed thermoelectric (TE) cooling and heating system, with a specific emphasis on its integration within circular manufacturing systems. The constructive feedback received

during my presentation was particularly beneficial. I gained fresh perspectives and valuable critiques that I intend to incorporate into my ongoing research. The interactive feedback sessions with peers and subject matter experts were instrumental in refining my research approach and broadening my knowledge base. Additionally, the program included practical sessions on the writing and structuring of EU project proposals. My active participation in these sessions was immensely beneficial, providing hands-on experience and critical insights into the complexities of research project documentation and funding acquisition. This knowledge is invaluable as I pursue future research opportunities and funding avenues. The program underscored the significance of interdisciplinary research and collaboration. Through various group activities and in-depth discussions, I developed a profound understanding of the synergies that emerge when diverse disciplines converge to address the multifaceted challenges of circular manufacturing. Evening activities, such as sightseeing and networking events, further enriched the program. These events facilitated informal interactions and the establishment of enduring professional relationships. A particularly memorable experience was the boat trip, which combined relaxation with the opportunity to engage in informal yet meaningful discussions about our work. In conclusion, the 2024 Circletech Summer School was a profoundly enriching professional experience. I highly recommend it to fellow researchers. The program's comprehensive curriculum, exceptional organization, and the opportunity to connect with a global network of experts provided an unparalleled platform for knowledge expansion and collaborative innovation in the field of circular manufacturing.

- The amount of programs was adequate, not too overwhelming. I suggest to organize more workshops/interactive programs
- Great event!

Written reflections on the questions “What could have been done differently? Who and how? Feel free to give constructive suggestions on how the next summer school could be improved?”

- The 9:00 beginning was a little bit early, because the location was hard to reach in time due to the bus schedule.
- For me some of the topics were not so relevant, but due to my other research topic. However, the presentation about funding options were very interesting for me. Thanks for the possibility being there.
- The audience can maintain attention better on a lecture, if you lower the lecture hours a little bit. I suggest to organize more informal social events (e.g. common sightseeing), where the participators from different universities can get to know each other.
- Thematic workshop events?

In summary, the summer school received positive feedback and evaluation this year as well. The schedule for June suited the participants better and the joint arrangements with the conference were successful. However, the workload, and the distribution between lectures, workshops and other more interactive activities, could be more honed. Spending time together, e.g. with city sightseeing, is still on the wish list, but this also requires the organizers to have local knowledge and the possibility to commit to evening activities too, among other responsibilities. The same goes with the arranging practical workshops (e.g. work in practice or utilizing software). Often the arranging of such an activity is limited by regulations related to occupational safety or copyright.

Outcomes of workshops

The task description of the Thursday and Friday workshops and the ideas that arose as a result of the groupwork are presented in Appendix 7.2.2.

4.5. Conclusions

The feedback and experiences of the previous summer school were made use of in planning Summer School 2 -- to the extent that it was reasonable and possible. The implementation of the arrangements differed slightly from the previous one, because the summer school 2 was organized in cooperation with the conference organizers. LUT has very functional event services, including facilities and catering, to support the organization of various events successfully -- and those were used with pleasure. Thus, based on LUT's experience, the biggest areas of development did not concern practical arrangements, such as the division of roles, work or responsibilities. The organizing team of the summer school was small and functional.

However, the biggest challenge was faced in building a smooth and whole thematic program. This was mainly due to the schedules of LUT's teaching and research staff (lecturers and summer school participants as well), which can be difficult to coordinate. Usually, the calendars have already been filled months in advance with overlapping activities and tasks. This presumably also makes it difficult to achieve the learning goals, when the participants are not able to focus only on the summer school. The organizer of the summer school noticed the same challenge among participants from outside LUT as well. Is multitasking currently the biggest obstacle to learning, and reason for decreased total work efficiency?

In summary, organizing the summer school was successful and the goals were achieved, i.e. the participants were somewhat satisfied with all measures.

5. Summer School 3: Multi-disciplinarity around Circular Economy (UNIM)

This section outlines the content and development process of the third Summer School. It presents the course objectives, describes the variety of activity formats implemented, and provides a detailed overview of the full program and schedule.

5.1. Program development

The third edition of the summer school was thoughtfully designed to provide researchers from diverse disciplines and at various career stages with the opportunity to engage in multidisciplinary topics related to energy research. It also aimed to equip participants with essential soft skills in research and innovation through a dynamic program that included a field visit, panel discussions, and interactive systems thinking workshops. There was a slight deviation from the original title of the summer school as the organizers saw an opportunity to design a program around energy topics to avoid repeating the previous summer school themes and create a multidisciplinary program.

Hosted by the University of Miskolc, the summer school was strategically aligned with the microCAD multidisciplinary research conference, creating a unique platform for extended engagement. Held on May 29, the microCAD conference enabled summer school participants to present their research findings, engage in cross-disciplinary discussions with a broader academic community, and explore cutting-edge developments in their respective fields.

In total, the summer school spanned five days, with one day dedicated to participation in the microCAD conference and the last day by organizing the scientific light hiking trip. To enrich the cultural and networking dimensions of the program, a group dinner was organized on the second day of the summer school (May 27), offering participants an informal setting to build connections and exchange ideas beyond the academic environment.

5.1.1. Date, times, and location

The summer school took place from Monday to Friday, May 26 – 30, 2025 at the University of Miskolc, Miskolci Egyetem 3515 MISKOLC, Egyetemváros.

5.1.2. Aim of the course

The summer school program was thoughtfully designed to offer to researchers at all career stages who are interested in deepening their knowledge of multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary approaches. It specifically targeted individuals working in fields related to energy engineering, waste management, economics, and the social sciences—domains where collaboration across disciplines is essential to address complex sustainability challenges.

The objectives of the summer school were to:

- Strengthen participants' research competencies by offering practical training, interactive sessions, and hands-on activities that enhance their ability to design and implement rigorous, impactful research.

- Broaden their understanding of interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary research by exposing them to diverse perspectives, methods, and frameworks relevant to current global challenges in energy and environmental transitions.
- Foster cross-disciplinary dialogue and collaboration through facilitated discussions, team-based exercises, and networking opportunities that encourage the co-creation of knowledge and the development of future research partnerships.
- Encourage critical thinking and systems-level analysis, equipping participants with the tools to approach complex problems holistically and to integrate social, economic, and technical dimensions in their research.
- Enhance soft skills essential for research and innovation, including communication, teamwork, and stakeholder engagement, thereby preparing participants for leadership roles in both academic and applied research settings.

5.1.3. Content development

To facilitate in-depth, interactive, and practice-oriented learning, the summer school incorporated a carefully curated set of activities. These were selected in collaboration with researchers from the University of Miskolc and partner universities, ensuring relevance across disciplinary backgrounds and alignment with participants' professional development needs. The summer school program included:

- Ten thematic lectures, covering a wide spectrum of perspectives: three from engineering disciplines, three from socio-economic fields, one addressing energy and environmental policy, and three delivered by industry experts offering practical insights from the field.
- Active participation in the microCAD conference, where summer school participants presented their research, engaged in academic discussions, and received valuable feedback from a broader community of researchers and professionals.
- An industrial field visit, organized in collaboration with a local industrial partner, provided participants with hands-on exposure to real-world practices in energy production and waste management.
- Two interactive systems thinking workshops, led by an expert from TU Delft, aimed at equipping participants with tools to analyse and address complex sustainability challenges from a holistic perspective.
- Three professional development sessions, including two focused trainings on research project management and one plenary session on international partnership building and networking, featuring best practices shared by experienced researchers.
- **A post-summer school event—the Science Café—is designed as an informal setting for participants to reflect on their experiences, share insights, and continue interdisciplinary dialogue beyond the structured sessions.
- We added a new dimension to summer school by offering a scientific light hiking to the Bukk mountains.

The mentioned activities are formed as the following programme:

3rd CIRCLETECH Summer School Programme

Monday, May 26, 2025

Time	Location	Activity / Topic	Lecturer
08:45	Main entrance	Meet in the main hall of the University – A4 building and walk to Fintelligence	Mohammad Jaber
09:00	Fintelligence	Ice breaker and opening of the summer school	Mohammad Jaber
09:20		Material Circulation in the Circular Economy: Engineering Heat Management Options for MSW Landfills	József Fajtli
10:00		Hydrogen as an Alternative Source of Energy for Industry and Households	Marianna Vadászi
10:40		Coffee break	
11:10		Pumped Hydro Storage for Clean Power, MVM	Molnár Ferenc
11:50		Lunch break	
13:00		Green Hydrogen Production in the Bükkábrány Energy Park	Kornél Kórán
13:40		Overview of hydrogen-related projects of Hungarian Gas Storage Ltd	Lajos Erdélyi
14:00		Coffee break	
14:30		The CRM Challenges of the Battery Industry and Technology Solutions	Sándor Nagy
15:10		Feedback discussion	

Tuesday, May 27, 2025

Time	Location	Activity	Lecturer
8:45	Main entrance	Meet in the main hall of the University – A4 building, and walk to the library	Mohammad Jaber
09:00	Library	Social Aspects of the Energy Transition	Ana Stojilovska
09:40	Lecture Hall	The Geopolitics Behind the Critical Raw Materials	Steffen Bettin
10:20		Coffee break	
10:50		China and CRMs (Market and Challenges)	Dániel Kuttor
11:20		Clean Industrial Act	David Peck
12:00		Lunch break	
12:00		Field trip	- Biogas-Miskolc Kft. (biogas plant in Miskolc) - Ecomissio Ltd (hazardous waste incinerator, Tiszaújváros)
16:00	Free time		
18:30	Dűlő Étterem	Social dinner	

Wednesday, May 28, 2025

Time	Location	Activity	Lecturer
09:00	Fintelligence	Whole System Mapping	Jeremy Faludi
11:30		Coffee break	
12:00		Twelve Leverage Points in Systems Thinking	Jeremy Faludi
13:00		Lunch break	
14:00		Open access and publication strategies	Beáta Szabóné Kovács
14:30		Exploitation of research results	György Czél
15:00		Coffee break	
15:30		International partnership building and networking strategies – panel discussion (Prof. Gábor Mucsi, Dr. Éva Hartai, Prof. Dr Norbert Zajzon, and Eszter Borsodi)	Aranka Földessy
16:15		Multidisciplinary scientific dialogue – Science café	

Thursday, June 29, 2025 - microCAD conference.

Friday, June 30, 2025 – Light Scientific Hiking in Lillafüred

5.1.4. Shared folder

- v
▢ Summer School UNIM May 2025
 - v
▢ Presentations
 - > ▢ May 26
 - > ▢ May 27
 - > ▢ May 28
 - > ▢ microCAD conference 0529
 - > ▢ Summer school photos

Figure 27 Second day group photo

5.2. Organization and staff

To ensure the effective organization and smooth delivery of the summer school, a dedicated project team at the University of Miskolc collaborated closely with university lecturers and representatives from partner institutions. A core team of five members was responsible for the overall coordination, supported by various colleagues for specific tasks and interactions.

The planning process involved extensive communication across departments and institutions, with clearly defined responsibilities. The core tasks carried out by the organizing team included:

Organizational and Logistical Tasks:

- Coordinating with project partners to determine the dates and times of the summer school
- Proposing accommodation options for participants traveling from other cities or countries
- Booking rooms and setting up guest Wi-Fi access
- Organizing lunches and coffee breaks
- Arranging necessary materials such as flip charts, post-its, markers, pointers, and cables
- Ensuring GDPR compliance and managing participant data
- Monitoring the summer school budget
- Troubleshooting logistical and technical issues during the event

Program Development and Participant Engagement:

- Designing the program content and activity formats
- Reaching out to instructors and guest speakers for contributions
- Sending formal invitations and program descriptions to prospective participants
- Preparing and distributing evaluation forms, and analyzing feedback post-event

- Gathering dietary preferences and logistical needs from participants
- Setting up a shared folder for distributing course materials and resources

On-Site Coordination and Communication:

- Welcoming participants and introducing the program
- Presenting speakers, instructors, and program elements
- Providing daily schedule updates and guiding the group across campus
- Delivering the opening and closing remarks of the summer school
- Facilitating smooth communication among participants, instructors, and organizing staff

Dissemination Activities:

- Sharing outcomes and highlights of the summer school with wider networks through appropriate dissemination channels

In addition to the core organizing team, a total of 13 instructors contributed to the academic and experiential learning aspects of the program. Their responsibilities included:

- Preparing and delivering lectures
- Organizing and leading field visits and campus tours
- Designing and conducting interactive workshops

Preparing assignments and facilitating group work

This section discusses the roles and associated tasks for organizing a summer school. It also lists all the instructors who were involved in the process.

Figure 28 Participants on the First day.

5.2.1. Organization

To organize the summer school successfully, the organization team assigned the roles. These can be summarized as follows:

Organizer (2)

- Determine the times and dates, together with project partners
- Propose accommodation options for those traveling from the partner universities.
- Prepare program contents and activities
- Reach out to instructors for contributions
- Send invitations and a description of the summer school to potential participants
- Set up a shared folder with course contents
- Analyse the evaluation forms
- Monitor the budget
- Organize gifts for the instructors/ contributors
- Manage GDPR requirements
- Request dietary preferences from participants
- Prepare a goodie bag with a nice book and/ or local souvenir for the participants

Moderator (1)

- Welcome the group
- Introduce the program, speakers/ instructors, and program elements
- Provide information about the schedule
- Lead the group between locations
- Lead tours (through the city, over the campus)
- Closing words of the summer school

Assistant (1)

- Book rooms
- Organize lunch and coffee
- Set up guest wifi
- Arrange post-its and flip-overs
- Arrange pointers and cables etc.,
- Troubleshooting.

Instructors (13)

- Prepare and deliver lectures
- Organize and lead tours
- Organize and deliver workshops
- Prepare and lead assignments

Disseminator (1)

- Create promotional materials
- Promote the summer school on social media
- Take photos
- Record videos
- Draft social media messages
- Distribute and collect the evaluation forms

Figure 29 Systems thinking workshop.

5.2.2. Instructors

József Faitli

Prof. Dr. József Faitli is a full professor and Head of the Department of Mechanical Process Engineering at the University of Miskolc, where he has worked since obtaining his mining engineering diploma in 1989. He earned his PhD (1998), habilitation (2016), and DSc from the Hungarian Academy of Sciences (2023), all summa cum laude.

His expertise lies in mechanical process engineering, particularly the flow of solid-liquid mixtures and the characterization of coarse disperse systems. He has held prestigious scholarships including Tempus, Fulbright, and the János Bolyai Research Scholarship.

Prof. Faitli has led or contributed to over 100 industrial R&D projects and 30 educational and research initiatives. He has supervised more than 80 theses and authored over 200 scientific publications, 27 technical works, and 14 patents. He has served as academic leader of international and national master's programs and is active in key European scientific committees on comminution, classification, and recycling.

Marianna Vadászi

Dr. Marianna Vadászi is Associate Professor and Head of the Natural Gas Engineering Department at the University of Miskolc, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Sciences and Engineering. With a PhD (2003), MBA (2010), and dual MSc degrees in petroleum/gas engineering and hydrogeology, she leads the university's Hydrogen Supply Engineer and Geothermal Engineer postgraduate training programs.

Her teaching and research focus on gas processing, underground gas storage, geothermal energy, and sustainable energy management. She has authored studies on clean energy transitions and co-authored the book Sustainability in a Holistic Approach. Her research includes underground hydrogen storage, hydrogen integration in gas systems, methane emissions reduction, mobile hydrogen delivery infrastructure, and carbon capture technologies.

Molnár Ferenc

Ferenc Molnár, PhD is an electrical engineer and energy expert with nearly 40 years of experience in the electricity sector. He currently serves as Advisor to the Deputy CEO of MVM Ltd. Infrastructure, focusing on workplace, operational, and labor safety across the group's companies. His expertise spans power plant investments, renewable energy, grid development, and energy storage technologies. Dr. Molnár has managed major projects including the life extension of the Paks Nuclear Power Plant and Hungary's first large-scale solar power installations. He teaches at Óbuda University and serves as President of the Renewable Energy Department at the Energy Management Scientific Association.

Kornél Kórán

is an experienced energy professional currently working on innovation and energy transition projects at Opus Energetika. He graduated as a petroleum engineer from the University of Miskolc and has accumulated over 15 years of experience across the energy sector, including upstream operations and natural gas transportation. In 2023, he earned an additional degree in Hydrogen Technology and Fuel Cell Engineering from the University of Pécs, deepening his expertise in emerging clean energy solutions.

At Opus Energetika, Kornél plays a key role in the implementation of strategic innovation projects, with a strong focus on advancing the company's green hydrogen production capabilities. His work reflects a commitment to sustainable energy development and the practical realization of Hungary's energy transition goals.

Lajos Erdélyi

After graduating from the Faculty of Chemical Engineering of the University of Veszprem, he was employed as a scholarship holder at MOL Ltd. in the Research and Production Division, where he worked on the development of crude oil and natural gas fields including underground gas storage operation. Since 2001, he has held a management role in areas related to the development and partly operation of domestic natural gas storage facilities at Hungarian Natural Gas Storage Company.

He has managed several key development projects in the life of underground gas storage facilities, ranging from investments to extend the service life to projects to significantly increase storage capacities. In his current role, as the head of MFGT's hydrogen-based projects, he ensures the implementation of its infrastructure investment and research and development program.

Sándor Nagy

Dr Sándor Nagy is an Associate Professor and the Director of the Institute of Raw Materials Preparation and Environmental Technology at the University of Miskolc, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Sciences and Engineering. He has been a dedicated member of the university since 2003, the same year he graduated with a degree in Process Engineering.

Dr Nagy's research interests are diverse and significant. They include the mechanical preparation of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) and End of Life Vehicles, the development of processing technologies for municipal solid wastes, other wastes, and biomasses, and the study of agglomeration. His contributions to these fields have been

invaluable, pushing the boundaries of knowledge and technology in environmental science and engineering.

Ana Stojilovska

Dr Ana Stojilovska is a Senior Research Fellow at the Institute for Political Science, HUN-REN Centre for Social Sciences, Hungary. She holds a PhD in Environmental Sciences and Policy from Central European University. Her research interests include an anthropological human-centered approach to studying energy poverty in the context of a socially just energy transition, and new governance models uncovering systematic drivers of energy vulnerability. Currently, she leads the Hungarian segment of the CERV-funded "Women in Solidarity for Energy" (WISE) project, promoting gender-inclusive energy transitions across seven European countries. She is also a Hungarian PD OTKA project leader exploring the impact of the energy crisis on small and medium enterprises and the public sector in Hungary.

Steffen Bettin

Steffen Bettin is a socio-economist and technology researcher working on pathways toward a fast and just sustainable energy transition. His work addresses energy innovations, digitalization, infrastructure, critical and advanced materials, as well as the political economy of power structures such as centralization and oligopolies. He examines the risks and opportunities of today's pressing challenges, particularly the complex structural ones that are both social and technical in nature.

Steffen studied economics in Heidelberg and Vienna and earned a PhD in Environmental Sciences and Policy from Central European University. Until recently, he was based at the Institute of Technology Assessment of the Austrian Academy of Sciences, where he also advised policymakers at both national and European levels—including the Austrian and European Parliaments. Recent contributions include a report on innovation in critical raw materials for the European Parliament's STOA Panel.

He also teaches an undergraduate course on the energy transition at WU Vienna University of Economics and Business and is a member of the editorial team of the interdisciplinary journal *Momentum Quarterly*.

Dániel Kuttor

Dr. Dániel Kuttor is an associate professor of regional economics at the University of Miskolc and co-director of its Confucius Institute, where he promotes Hungarian-Chinese cooperation in academia, business, and culture. He holds a PhD in spatial analysis of Central European economies and has led several EU and Visegrad Fund projects. His research focuses on industrial restructuring, regional disparities, and Chinese investment in Hungary, especially in Northern Hungary's economic revitalization. He speaks English, German, and basic Chinese.

David Peck

Dr. David Peck researches and teaches, cross-faculty, in the fields of critical materials and circular design, in particular, developing remanufacturing. He is a founding member of the TU Delft Critical Raw Materials working group and the TU Delft Circular Built Environment Hub. In addition, David works in Estonian Business School, Tallinn, Estonia. He is also a visiting Professor with Coventry University, Centre for Business in Society. David is a founding partner and director of Defence Invest. David is an Executive Board Member for EIT Raw Materials and ERMA. David also works with ad hoc committees in the European Union in Brussels, The

Netherlands Government in The Hague, and is a Horizon Europe reviewer. David sits on the steering committee for the European Remanufacturing Council. He is the TU Delft lead scientist for EU Horizon Europe & Horizon 2020 projects CiRCLETECH, Pop Machina, ProSUM, ERN and FP7 CRM_Innonet. David is TU Delft scientific leader for the EU KIC EIT Raw Materials, representing the university in the programme. David sits on the TU Delft Critical Materials core working group, developing TU Delft actions in the field.

Jeremy Faludi

Dr. Faludi teaches sustainable design at TU Delft, and has taught at Stanford, Dartmouth, and elsewhere. His Autodesk Sustainability Workshop videos have had over 5 million views from 140 countries, and he has contributed to six books, including *Worldchanging: a User's Guide to the 21st Century*. He designed the first version of the biomimicry database Asknature.org. Over 30 companies have used his Whole System Mapping method, and he wrote the OECD's recommendations to governments on green 3D printing.

Beata Szabone Kovacs

Acting general director, senior librarian at the University of Miskolc Library, Archives, and Museum. In her work, in addition to traditional library services, she also focuses on electronic information services and access to information. She is focusing on the activities of libraries in support of research and publishing, and the integration of new opportunities, especially open science/access, into the workflow of a University library.

Czél György

Professor György Czél is a tenured professor in polymer technology at the University of Miskolc and an Academic Professor. He holds multiple advanced degrees, including two PhDs and a Dr. habil in engineering. With extensive experience in research, innovation, and education, he leads a research group focused on polymer and energy technologies, supervises PhD and MSc students, and has obtained numerous grants, including NKFI-funded projects. His work bridges academia and industry, emphasizing experimental design, innovation, and knowledge transfer.

Éva Hartai

Éva Hartai is Honorary Professor at the Institute of Exploration Geosciences, University of Miskolc. Éva is a geologist, MSc from Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, PhD from the Technical University of Košice, Slovakia. 'Eurogeologist' title holder since 2009. Her research area is geology, geochemistry, and mineral resources. She has 45 years of teaching experience at the University of Miskolc. For more than a decade, she was the coordinator of the European Federation of Geologists' Panel of Experts on Education and the editor-in-chief of the European Geologist journal. She has taken part in numerous EU-funded and national projects, having a leading role in these projects.

Norbert Zajzon

Dr. Norbert Zajzon is Professor and Head of the Department of Geology and Mineral Resources at the University of Miskolc, Hungary. He holds an MSc (2001) and PhD (2006) from Eötvös Loránd University, with research focused on instrumental mineralogy and geochemistry related to global environmental crises.

He teaches mineralogy, ore deposits, and planetary sciences, and leads the university's microprobe and 3D labs. Dr. Zajzon has coordinated major EU-funded projects such as

UNEXMIN, UNEXUP, and Robominers, advancing robotic mineral exploration. He also serves as Chief Secretary of the Hungarian Geological Society and is a Fellow of the Society of Economic Geologists.

Prof. Dr. Gábor Mucsi

PROF. DR. GÁBOR MUCSI has been involved in educational, research, development, and innovation tasks related to environmental industry and waste recycling issues for 22 years. During this time, more than 330 scientific publications have been published, which have received more than 1200 independent citations. His research areas include the preparation and utilization of solid waste, in a narrower sense, the mechanical activation of industrial waste (slag, fly ash, construction waste) to control their reactivity, the development of geopolymers, and the synergistic utilization of waste. Since 2020, he has been the Dean of the Faculty of Earth and Environmental Sciences and Engineering of the University of Miskolc, a university professor at the Institute of Raw Material Preparation and Environmental Technology. Before that, he was the scientific deputy dean of the faculty for seven years. He is the president of the Cement Division of the Silicate Industry Scientific Association. So far, more than 120 TDK papers, theses, diploma projects, and dissertations have been prepared under his professional guidance. So far, he has been involved in a total of 73 industrial R&D projects and 36 grant projects, in many cases in a leadership role. He has participated as a guest lecturer at foreign universities 14 times.

5.3. Participation

This section provides information on the selection process, invitations, and follow-up.

5.3.1. Recruitment of participants

To recruit the participants of the summer school, the organizers created a registration form using Microsoft Forms and an Excel sheet. The Excel sheet was shared with partner universities and researchers who have an IDP at the University of Miskolc. The registration form was sent to all the PhD students at the University of Miskolc through the Neptun system, which is used for university official communication and other administrative tasks for the students.

By the end of the registration period, 22 participants registered in the summer school. Additionally, registered participants were offered the opportunity to take part in the microCAD conference to present their latest results with peers. No fees were requested for registering for the summer school, and the conference fees were waived for the summer school participants.

5.3.2. Channels and points of contact

To contact the participants of the summer school, the team mainly used email to send the important information, the program, and presentations to the participants. Moreover, the LinkedIn page was used to advertise the programme and the guest lecturers of the summer school.

Once arriving in Miskolc, the organizers provided the participants with the necessary information related to the city, and at the university, we guided them around the buildings to show them the lecture rooms. After the summer school, the participants received all workshop and lecture materials through the shared folder.

5.4. Dissemination and evaluation

5.4.1. Dissemination

Prior to the summer school, information about the summer school was shared in relevant research groups (related to circular economy) at the three participating universities, to attract participants.

During and after the summer school, LinkedIn posts were created to inform our network about the summer school activities and content.

Figure 30 LinkedIn post announcement on the summer school.

5.4.2. Evaluation

To evaluate the third summer school, we asked the participants to fill out a survey made on Microsoft Forms and shared by email. In total, we received 14 responses, and a brief overview can be shown as follows:

1. What is your current academic/professional status?

[More details](#)

● Young researcher - PhD student	9
● Postdoctoral researcher	2
● Faculty member	3

Figure 31 Participants' current professional status.

2. How did you learn about the summer school?

[More details](#)

● University/department email	10
● Recommendation	3
● CIRCLETECH website	1

Figure 32 How the participants registered to the summer school

3. Attending the summer school brought me about:

[More details](#)

● Very little ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● Very much

- Interested in creating new joint research
- My research skills evolved
- My communication and networking skills evolved
- My knowledge on thematic and relevant topics increased

Figure 33 Feedback on joining the summer school

4. Please rate the following on a scale from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree):

[More details](#)

● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5

- The duration of the summer school was appropriate
- The dates of the summer school fit well in my schedule
- The workload during the summer school was appropriate
- The number of lecture hours was appropriate
- The summer school was well organized
- The time management of the courses was appropriate
- The content of the summer school was appropriate

Figure 34 General Feedback on the Summer School

5. Which activity did you enjoy the most? Please rate the following on a scale from 1 (Very Poor) to 5 (Excellent):

[More details](#)

● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5

- Ice breaker and opening (M. Jaber)
- MSW Landfills (J. Faitli)
- Hydrogen for Industry (M. Vadász)
- Pumped Hydro Storage (F. Molnár)
- MOL-Hydrogen (T. Méró)
- Hungarian Gas Storage (L. Erdélyi)
- Battery Industry Challenges (S. Nagy)
- Social Aspects of Energy Transition (A. Stojilovska)
- Geopolitics of CRMs (S. Bettin)
- China and CRMs (D. Kuttor)
- Clean Industrial Act (D. Peck)
- Field trip (Biogas & Ecomissio)
- Whole System Mapping (J. Faludi)
- Twelve Leverage Points (J. Faludi)
- Open Access & Publication Strategies (B. Szabóné Kovács)
- Exploitation of Research Results (G. Czél)
- Networking Panel (A. Földessy)
- Science Café

Figure 35 Feedback on every single activity of the summer school

6. In general, what did you particularly like?

14 Responses

ID ↑	Name	Responses
1	anonymous	The dinner
2	anonymous	I hoped I would attend more
3	anonymous	The workshop with Jeremy was great
4	anonymous	Trips are always fun!
5	anonymous	Networking
6	anonymous	I really like everything and learnt a lot!
7	anonymous	The first day of the summer school
8	anonymous	My favorite part was the industrial visit and the practical lessons at wednesday
9	anonymous	Friendly atmosphere
10	anonymous	It was good in general
11	anonymous	The interdisciplinary
12	anonymous	Atmosphere of discussion, tematic issues, and scientific exposure to high level researchers and lecturers
13	anonymous	Networking, Teamworking
14	anonymous	The panels were very light and informative/ the organization was good too/ the diversity of the topics

Figure 36 Feedback on what the participants liked about the summer school.

7. In general, what could be improved?

14 Responses

1	anonymous	AV systems
2	anonymous	The time it is held .it clashes with other crucial university programs
3	anonymous	More interactive sessions
4	anonymous	I felt like the hydrogen lectures were more sales pitches for potential shareholders. Also they repeated each other a couple of times. I also don't think that doing lectures the whole day generally works. I prefer a bit of variety (e.g. 2 hours lectures + 2 hours of workshop)
5	anonymous	More days and research related topics
6	anonymous	Nothing, it was nice!
7	anonymous	nothing, everything was perfect
8	anonymous	Technical instuments should be tested and check before
9	anonymous	timing
10	anonymous	Nothing specific
11	anonymous	Some presenter speaking
12	anonymous	Socialization: it would be more ideal if the event can also invite the very high reputable institution more than one [not just TU-DELFT & LUT University]
13	anonymous	More guest lecturers from different universities
14	anonymous	maybe it would be better to include more balanced sessions between social science and engineering

Figure 37 Participants' feedback on what could be improved in the summer school

5.5. Conclusions

UNIM Summer School focused on diversity, interactive participation, and balance between structure and flexibility. As a result of formulating the summer school in this way, we have several conclusions and experiences:

1. Group breaks provide meaningful interactions across participants from different institutions and cultures.
2. Having a multidisciplinary form of summer school structure provided a forum where researchers from technical and socio-economic backgrounds could have the chance to discuss how to solve problems through different approaches.

3. Coordinating with guest lecturers can be time-consuming for the organizers, but timely messages and feedback helped bring the best experiences from academia and industry.
4. Summer schools can involve scientific and cultural activities to give the participants the space to interact with each other on the professional and personal levels.

6. Conclusions

This document discussed the approaches to develop and organize the summer schools, the content of the summer schools, an evaluation, and the lessons learnt. It also give insight into how participants were attracted, which instructors contributed to the contents and how different channels were used to communicate about the summer schools.

The three partners each had a leading and coordinating role in developing one of the summer schools. This resulted in having three distinct approaches in realizing the content and programs. The top aims for organizing the summer schools were to start in-depth academic discussions around a desired topic, while bringing researchers with different backgrounds and perspectives together. The summer schools program were developed to accommodate both aims. General objectives for the summer schools were to learn about research methods, gain experience in project proposal and consortium development, working in an interactive environment, and develop researcher's communication skills.

Specific objectives of the first summer school on Circular Manufacturing were to develop an understanding of low carbon transition technologies for design and manufacturing, (critical) materials concerns, and waste elimination. As well as to gain insight into existing circular design theories and methods to enable circular strategies to be enacted. Generally seen, the summer school went as planned and the feedback from the participants has been very positive. Several generic conclusions can be drawn which are useful in organizing summer schools in the future. The first is to make sure to have enough people to organize the summer school as in entails a broad range of tasks. Besides, having a variety of presenters and types of activities, and include tours and practical lab work, will increase participant engagement. With regards to the schedule, making sure to have enough 'air' in the schedule allows participants to connect to each other and to the city. Make sure the participants get time to digest what they've been exposed to during the day. The final point, which is relevant to upcoming summer schools, is to align the summer school program and content with the CiRCLETECH research group activities.

The Summer School 2 combined interdisciplinary thematic lectures, an international conference and workshop sessions around the theme of Processing technologies in materials recycling, particularly Critical Raw Materials. This offered diverse learning objectives that researchers at different career stages could benefit from. The summer school brought together researchers from juniors to professors from different disciplines and enabled creating of new contacts and networks for consortiums - and developing of research ideas further to project proposals. Summer School attendees developed their research skills in practice by participating in conference with posters and pitch speeches. At the same time, this provided an opportunity for interdisciplinary networking. Similarly, research skills were developed in group work in workshops, where researchers from different fields discussed research ideas and proposals for EU Horizon calls.

The Summer School 2 was a great success overall, based on feedback from both the organizing committee and the participants. Participants were highly motivated. In the survey, participants rated the summer school with high scores, over 4/5 in all areas: content, learning outcomes, timing and event arrangements. Of course, there is room for improvement. Arrangements started early will facilitate the availability of lecturers and the smooth running of the schedule. Although the program also included workshop activities, many participants could benefit from more interactive activities instead of traditional lectures. Many also appreciate a more informal (evening) program that allows for getting to know each other and creates connections for lasting collaboration.

The 3rd CiRCLETECH Summer School successfully brought together early-career researchers and faculty from engineering, social sciences, and policy fields, addressing topics such as energy transition, circular economy, critical raw materials (CRMs), and sustainability from various perspectives. Participants overwhelmingly reported increased knowledge in thematic areas, enhanced research skills, and improved communication and networking abilities. Most rated the content, organization, and speaker quality highly, with scores averaging between 4 and 5 on a 5-point scale. The format provided ample opportunities for international networking. Many attendees expressed interest in collaborative research projects, with the Science Café, field trip, and panel discussions identified as effective platforms for informal exchange and idea generation. Participants commended the organization, time management, and structure of the program. Icebreaker sessions, field visits, and the interactive workshops (particularly with Dr. Jeremy Faludi) were highlighted as favorites.

While the duration was generally viewed as appropriate, some participants suggested that the timing conflicted with other academic commitments (e.g., exams). Future editions could consider mid-summer dates or earlier planning to prevent such overlaps. Several attendees recommended balancing lecture-heavy sessions with more interactive elements such as workshops, group exercises, or case-based discussions to maintain engagement and accommodate different learning styles. Although the presence of institutions like TU Delft and LUT University was appreciated, participants expressed a desire for more diverse academic representation, including additional top-ranked or globally renowned institutions. A few technical issues (e.g., audiovisual systems) were noted. Ensuring that all technical equipment is tested in advance would improve the participant experience, especially in hybrid or recorded sessions. Some participants felt that certain industry-focused presentations leaned too much toward promotional content. Providing clear guidance to guest speakers on maintaining academic and technical rigor would help preserve the scientific tone.

Expected impact

Organizing summer schools can be a learning experience for both organizers and participants. Organizing summer school has an impact on research collaborations by motivating participants to discuss new research ideas and exposing them to real-world examples. As such, they can link their research experiences and real-world needs. Summer schools are a source of rapid knowledge transfer as participants and lecturers are exposed to cutting-edge themes in science, which can influence them in teaching, publication, and innovation activities. Further, it is a good example of building capacity as it strengthens the participants' scientific communication abilities, systems and critical thinking, and interdisciplinary analysis, which are skills needed for addressing global sustainability challenges. Lastly, by interacting with practitioners, participants gained insight into how academic research can translate into policy-relevant outputs.

Next steps

Building on our experience in planning, organizing, and coordinating summer schools, we foresee several steps to take in the future:

1. Keep the momentum resulting from the summer school and expand the institutional network. It would be beneficial for the partners to seek new collaborations with new universities beyond CiRCLETECH in the long run and organize more summer/winter schools.

2. Learning from participants' feedback and organizers' reflections, future summer schools would benefit from a more interactive format and workshops other than lecture-based summer schools.
3. Ensure a better balance between technical/engineering content and social, behavioral, or policy-related themes, as this approach is needed in solving current issues, especially around the themes of circular economy and just transition narratives.

7. Appendix

7.1. Evaluation – Summer school 1

7.1.1. Online evaluation form – Summer School 1

10/27/23, 3:44 PM

Evaluation form

Evaluation form

First CIRCLETECH Summer School - Circular Manufacturing - 22-25 May 2023

Your name

Your answer

Your function

Your answer

Your expertise (in keywords)

Your answer

Why did you attend the Summer School?

- Compulsory (elective) course
- Interest
- Teacher(s)
- Relevant topic(s)
- Stay abroad
- Other:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf6xFDmb_5oVHNQBR9T6GvA7Tjr7xK7a33iCrTr_GiRQEsYKQ/viewform

1/12

Where did you hear about the Summer School?

- Home university
- Other participants
- Internet (project web page)
- Host university
- Former participants
- Other:

Organization of the Summer School

The duration of the Summer School was appropriate.

strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 strongly disagree

○ ○ ○ ○ ○

The dates of the Summer School fit well in my schedule.

strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 strongly disagree

○ ○ ○ ○ ○

The workload during the Summer School was appropriate.

strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 strongly disagree

○ ○ ○ ○ ○

The number of lecture hours was appropriate.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

The Summer School was well organized.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

The time management of the courses was appropriate.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

Additional
Remarks

Your answer

Content and quality of the lectures

My previous knowledge was sufficient to understand the lectures.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

The content of the lectures was sufficiently exemplified with practical work and / or excursions.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

The content of the lectures was well illustrated with examples.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

There were sufficient cross-links between the different lectures to understand the coherence.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

My state of knowledge is substantially higher than before the Summer School.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

The didactic tools (projector, blackboard, etc.) supported the lectures in a useful way.

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly disagree				

The teaching materials (slides, etc.) were clearly structured.

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly disagree				

The speed of knowledge transfer was appropriate.

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly disagree				

The lectures were rich in variety.

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly disagree				

The atmosphere during the lectures was pleasant.

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	strongly disagree				

Additional remarks (optional):

Your answer

Which activities did you enjoy most?

- Tue: Personal grant development 1/4 - Nela Kapelan
- Tue: Lecture 1/8: Circular Manufacturing - Jan-Henk Welink
- Tue: Circular Design Method 1/2: Remanufacturing Checklist - Nina Boorsma and Jan-Henk Welink
- Tue: Circular Design Method 2/2: Circular Product Readiness method - Nina Boorsma and Jan-Henk Welink
- Wed: Lecture (online) 2/8: Scientific writing - Prof. Norbert Sabó
- Wed: Lecture 3/8: Open science practices - Beáta Kovács Szabóné
- Wed: Personal grant development 2/4 – Preparation of a grant: Personal vs Collaborative - Jan Schiereck and Frank Versluis
- Wed: Lecture 4/8: Model for asset manufacturers: Eco-cost vs. lifecycle costs - Jenny Coenen
- Wed: Lecture 5/8: Driving and encouraging sustainability through Emerson factory automation - Diana Precup
- Wed: Lecture 6/8: Industrial and policy trends - Jan-Henk Welink
- Wed: Lecture 7/8: Resources for circular manufacturing - Jan-Henk Welink
- Thu: Workshop 1/2: Remanufacturing in practice - Jenny Coenen and Marten Bootsma
- Thu: Lecture (online) 8/8: Sustainable solutions in Power Tool development - József Kakuk
- Thu: Personal grant development 3-4/4 – Grant writing: tips, assignments, discussions - Nela Kapelan

Explanation (optional):

Your answer

Which lectures did you enjoy less or could be improved?

- Tue: Personal grant development 1/4 - Nela Kapelan
- Tue: Lecture 1/8: Circular Manufacturing - Jan-Henk Welink
- Tue: Circular Design Method 1/2: Remanufacturing Checklist - Nina Boorsma and Jan-Henk Welink
- Tue: Circular Design Method 2/2: Circular Product Readiness method - Nina Boorsma and Jan-Henk Welink
- Wed: Lecture (online) 2/8: Scientific writing - Prof. Norbert Sabó
- Wed: Lecture 3/8: Open science practices - Beáta Kovács Szabóné
- Wed: Personal grant development 2/4 – Preparation of a grant: Personal vs Collaborative - Jan Schiereck and Frank Versluis
- Wed: Lecture 4/8: Model for asset manufacturers: Eco-cost vs. lifecycle costs - Jenny Coenen
- Wed: Lecture 5/8: Driving and encouraging sustainability through Emerson factory automation - Diana Precup
- Wed: Lecture 6/8: Industrial and policy trends - Jan-Henk Welink
- Wed: Lecture 7/8: Resources for circular manufacturing - Jan-Henk Welink
- Thu: Workshop 1/2: Remanufacturing in practice - Jenny Coenen and Marten Bootsma
- Thu: Lecture (online) 8/8: Sustainable solutions in Power Tool development - József Kakuk
- Thu: Personal grant development 3-4/4 – Grant writing: tips, assignments, discussions - Nela Kapelan

Explanation (optional):

Your answer

Teachers

The linguistic style of the teachers was fluent and clear.

strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 strongly disagree

Difficult facts were explained in a comprehensive way.

strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 strongly disagree

The teachers appeared well prepared.

strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 strongly disagree

The students had the opportunity to participate actively.

strongly agree 1 2 3 4 5 strongly disagree

The teachers motivated the students to an active participation (e.g. by asking questions).

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

The teachers took enough time to answer questions.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

Additional remarks (optional):

Your answer

Practical work / excursions

The size of the working groups was appropriate.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

The supervision by the teachers was appropriate.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

The atmosphere during the practical work and the excursions was pleasant.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

The number of excursions was appropriate.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

The number of practical work hours was appropriate.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

The level of the courses was appropriate.

1 2 3 4 5
strongly agree strongly disagree

Additional remarks (optional):

Your answer

10/27/23, 3:44 PM

Evaluation form

In general, what did you particularly like?

Your answer

In general, what could be improved?

Your answer

Thank you!

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11/12

7.1.2. Participant report by Dr. Péter Veres – Summer School 1

REPORT

from the Summer School of TU Delft

Location: Delft University of Technology (TU Delft)

Duration: 22.05.2023-25.05.2023

Short summary: One-week summer school training mainly for students (Bsc, Msc, PhD) on the theoretical, legal, economic, and practical implementation of the circular economy/production.

Report:

As part of the CircleTech project, it was possible for several people from the University of Miskolc to participate in the summer university held at the Delft University of Technology, to which I applied with interest. Even then, the pre-prepared program seemed well-structured and professional. Later, minimal changes were made to it, but this did not detract from its value. 10-14 students were present at the trainings: in addition to the Hungarians there were Finnish and Danish students. The main topic of the summer university is circular production, into which we got a deep insight. Several lecturers and researchers gave presentations; we heard about the new developments not only from the University of Delft, but also from the Universities of Miskolc, The Hague and Rotterdam, as well as the company Bosch from Miskolc. The topics of the program's lectures and exercises were as follows:

- Current global emissions and recycling situation in theory, practice and regulations, highlighting critical raw materials.
- Description of technologies with low CO2 emissions and their application.
- Circular strategies and planning, as well as customer attitudes towards recycled and remanufactured products.
- Practical tasks, in which we have to disassemble components, as well as to understand, standardize and facilitate it.
- Group work, in which the task was to assess, analyze and propose ideas, with the help of a questionnaire to companies in the direction of environmental awareness and circular production.
- The speakers also presented the theoretical and practical initiation and implementation of consortia, project work, and their financing, as well as work in research groups.
- Research methods and the possibilities and principles of publishing were also presented.

In addition to the lectures, we were taken to various buildings of the University of Delft, in which we saw the developments and laboratories of the various sectors, such as the automation, water hull simulation, architecture/interior design, or the place called "Green Village", where new technologies get tested, by people to their effectiveness and practicality.

Apart from the professional side of the trip, we gained insight into the local customs and way of life, which is much more balanced, conscious, and environmentally friendly than what we are used to.

Thank you for the opportunity to travel, because my knowledge has expanded both professionally and culturally, and I look forward to further opportunities.

Dr. Péter Veres

7.1.3. Participat report by Dr. Ákos Cservenák – Summer School 1

Report

Event: Summer School 2023

Location: TU Delft, The Netherlands

Duration: 22-25 May 2023

Summary of content:

The CircleTech project provided the opportunity to participate in a research trip to the Netherlands. The main part of the trip lasted for 3 days, during which we had the opportunity to learn about circular manufacturing and to visit a part of the Dutch university. I myself am less familiar with circular manufacturing, but this gave me a lot of interesting and useful information. Apart from circular manufacturing, there were also presentations on other topics that were worth listening to also as a post-doctoral lecturer and researcher. One of these was "Criteria for quality publications", where a presentation showed us point by point how to write such a publication. We were also given an insight into EU funding opportunities, both in the form of consortia and individual grants. In addition to the topics covered in the presentations, the event also provided a useful opportunity to build new contacts with participants from the Dutch and Finnish partner universities. In conclusion, this event was an excellent opportunity to launch the collaborations planned in the project and to organize further joint events.

Thank you for the opportunity and I look forward to further opportunities!

Dr. Ákos Cservenák

7.1.4. Participant report by Eszter Borsodi – Summer School 1

1st CiRCLETECH Summer school – 2023: Circular Manufacturing

22 May 2023 16:00 CEST - 25 May 2023 18:00 CEST, Delft University of Technology, Delft, the Netherlands

Eszter Borsodi

PhD student

University of Miskolc

Institute of Machine and Product Design

Speakers: Dr. David Peck, Dr. Nina Boorsma, Nela Kapelan, Prof. Jenny Coenen, Marten Bootsma, Jan-Henk Welink, Jan Schiereck, Frank Versluis,

Topics: Circular Manufacturing design methodologies; Remanufacturability assessment methods; Good practices; Useful tips for a research career; How to write competitive proposals and receive research grants

New contacts: Jan-Henk Welink J.H.Welink@tudelft.nl, Nina Boorsma N.E.Boorsma@tudelft.nl, Nela Kapelan N.Kapelan@tudelft.nl

During the three days in Delft, we listened to lectures mainly on the topic of Circular Manufacturing. There were also speakers from the academic life and corporates. Practical methods were also presented by them and which we applied in practice as part of group work. The participants of the summer school came from different research areas, so it was very interesting to discuss a topic from different points of view. The last day of the summer school was a workshop: our task was to go through the points of a remanufacturability assessment method to analyze how difficult it is to disassemble various electronic devices (e.g.: television) and later recycle, remanufacture, or refurbish its parts.

In addition to the topic of Circular Manufacturing, we were also able to learn important knowledge for a career as a researcher, such as tips related to research grants and

scholarships, which proved to be very useful for me as a first-year PhD student. The summer school was also a good opportunity to exchange ideas and build international partnerships, to practice the professional language, and of course to get to know other cultures.

Overall, I think this program can be a great starting point for future joint research and collaborations with researchers from the participating Finnish and Dutch universities.

7.2. Evaluation – Summer school 2

7.2.1. Online evaluation form – Summer School 2

CiRCLETECH Summer School 2, June 10-14 2024: Processing technologies in materials recycling Feedback survey

Mandatory questions are marked with a star (*)

Questions 1 to 8 will reflect your own participation in the Summer School, including Xplorer conference.

1. My role in the Summer School was:

- Attendee or student
- Lecturer or coach
- Organizer
- Other

2. My motivation over the Summer School was:

Scale: 1 - very little, 5 - very high. *

	1	2	3	4	5	Can't say
Choose	<input type="radio"/>					

3. How much did you invest in this event? (Note that tasks may be e.g. meetings with colleagues.) *

- I neither participated in the events nor completed the tasks.
- I didn't participate actively in the events, but I completed the tasks.
- I somewhat participated and/or completed some of the tasks.
- I somewhat participated and/or completed all the tasks.
- I participated in almost all events and/or completed the tasks.

4. Attending the Summer School brought me about:

Scale: 1 - very little, 5 - very much. *

	1	2	3	4	5	Can't say
Interested in creating new joint research	<input type="radio"/>					
My research skills evolved	<input type="radio"/>					
My communication and networking skills evolved	<input type="radio"/>					
My knowledge on thematics and relevant topics increased	<input type="radio"/>					

5. Additional remarks, thoughts and feelings on your expectations, achievements or disappointments concerning the Summer School:

The following questions 6 to 10 will evaluate the organization of the Summer School.

6. The overall timing of the Summer School was appropriate.

Scale: 1 - strongly disagree, 5 - strongly agree. *

	1	2	3	4	5	Can't say
Five days duration	<input type="radio"/>					
Dates fit well in my calendar/schedule	<input type="radio"/>					

7. The content of the Summer School was appropriate.

Scale: 1 - strongly disagree, 5 - strongly agree *

	1	2	3	4	5	Can't say
Joint events (Summer School and Xplorer conference) worked well together	<input type="radio"/>					
Lecture topics were important and interesting	<input type="radio"/>					
<hr/>						
	1	2	3	4	5	Can't say
The used teaching methods promoted my learning	<input type="radio"/>					

8. The workload during the Summer School was appropriate.

Scale: 1 - strongly disagree, 5 - strongly agree *

	1	2	3	4	5	Can't say
The number of lecture hours	<input type="radio"/>					
The number of laboratory visits	<input type="radio"/>					
Time management - number of breaks	<input type="radio"/>					
Social events / leisure time	<input type="radio"/>					

9. The Summer School was well organized.

Scale: 1 - strongly disagree, 5 - strongly agree *

	1	2	3	4	5	Can't say
Facilities, lecture rooms and used tools	<input type="radio"/>					
Food and coffee	<input type="radio"/>					
Other help and services	<input type="radio"/>					
The overall atmosphere was pleasant	<input type="radio"/>					

10. What could have been done differently? Who and how? Feel free to give constructive suggestions on how the next summer school could be improved.

7.2.2. Outcomes of workshops – Summer School 2

The short Group Assignment – Horizon Europe, 100bn Euro of opportunity.

Assignment. A Funding proposal short overview document. You will be assigned into groups for this assignment.

You will need to find EU funding calls via this link; <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-search>;

You will be guided and supported in class as to what you are looking for.

You will need to select one funding call based on the themes of the course; business reporting, supply chain, materials, critical materials, circularity, sustainability, metals, low carbon transition, low carbon energy tech, etc.

Writing a short overview of the concept of your proposal to address the call you have selected:

Your deliverable is to write a short document, typically one A4 page of text, although the document may be longer as you use images, diagrams, to explain your proposal in response to the call.

Figure 38 Group assignment description for workshop.

Figure 39 The first ideas of the workshop groups on the white board.

HORIZON-CL5-2025-D2-03-SRP: Sustainable processing and refining of raw materials to produce battery grade Li-ion battery materials (Batt4EU Partnership)

- **Partners:**
 - BASF, BOLIDEN, BMW, LUT, TU Delft, Miskolc, TU Freiberg
- **Who we are**
 - Should this describe LUT as a whole or the most relevant research groups / departments (LENS+LES+Social Sciences)
- **Work packages**
 - 4 or 5 WPs + a project management WP if the budget is ca. 6 million EUR

Call for proposals

Achieving global leadership in climate-neutral, circular and digitised digital value chains (Manufacturing)

Call for proposal number:

HORIZON-CL4-2025-INDUSTRY-01-01

Call title:

Integrated approaches for remanufacturing (Made in Europe Partnership) (IA)

Partners: Hungary, The Netherlands, South Korea

Universities:

Companies:

Budget request:

€ 6 million – This budget will support the remanufacturing of the thermoelectric modul which is used in the automotive industry (cooling and heating the lightning system, seat heating, driving system heating and warming, etc.).

Expected outcome: double the capacity to remanufacture in the EU, leading to enhanced industrial resilience, competitiveness and strategic autonomy; and support skills and education capabilities for remanufacturing.

Framework: Ecodesign for Sustainable Product Regulation, EU waste/sectoral legislation, Digital Product Passport, ecodesign approach

Figure 40 Some one-pager drafts presented.